

Optimization and Evaluation of Capecitabine Loaded Niosomal Drug Delivery System

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Abstract:

Niosomes are non-ionic surfactant vesicles obtained on hydration of synthetic nonionic surfactants, with or without incorporation of cholesterol or their lipids. They are vesicles systems similar to liposomes that can be used as carriers of amphiphilic and lipophilic drugs. Niosomes are promising vehicle for drug delivery and being non-ionic and niosomes are biodegradable, biocompatible non-immunogenic and exhibit flexibility in their structural characterization. Niosomes have been widely evaluated for controlled release and targeted delivery for the treatment of cancer, viral infections and other microbial disease. Niosomes can entrap hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs and can prolong the circulation of the entrapped drug in body. This review article focuses on the advantages, Disadvantages, preparation methods, factor affecting, characterizations, invitro methods, drug release kinetics, and applications of niosome.

Keywords: Niosomes, conventional therapy, polymer

Introduction:

Paul Ehrlich, in 1909, initiated the development for targeted delivery when he envisaged a drug delivery mechanism that would target directly to diseased cell. Drug targeting can be defined as the ability to direct a therapeutic agent specifically to desired site of action with little or no interaction with non-target tissue. The concept of incorporating the drug into niosome for a better targeting of the drug at appropriate tissue destination is widely accepted by researchers and academicians. Various types of drug deliveries can be possible using niosomes like targeting, ophthalmic, topical, parental, etc.

Novel Drug Delivery System:

In the past few decades, considerable attention has been focused on the development of novel drug delivery system (NDDS). The NDDS should ideally fulfil two prerequisites. Firstly, it should deliver the drug at a rate directed by the needs of the body, over the period of treatment. Secondly, it should channel the active entity to the site of action.

Merits of NDDS:

Reduces the total amount of drug administered over the period of drug treatment, so it reduces the systemic and local side effects.

Targeting of the drug molecule towards the tissue (or) organ reduces the toxicity to the normal tissues.

Improved patient compliance resulting from the reduction in the frequency of doses required to maintain the desired therapeutic response.

Limitations of novel drug delivery system:

To reach previously in accessible domains e.g. intra cellular site, bacteria, viruses, parasites etc.

To protect the drug and the body from one another until it reaches at the desired site of action.

To control the frequency and rate of drug delivery at the pharmacological receptor.

Drug delivery carrier:

Carriers are used to achieve targeted drug delivery. Carrier is one of the special molecule or system essentially required for effective transportation of loaded drug up to the preselected sites.

Salient features of niosomes

Niosomes act as alternatives of liposomes.

Osmotically active and stable.

Niosome increases the stability of entrapped drug.

They can be made to reach the site of action by oral, parenteral as well as topical routes.

Materials And Methods:

Capecitabine is a nucleoside metabolic inhibitor with anti-neoplastic activity.

Methods of preparation of niosomes

Ether injection method

Thin film hydration technique

Sonication method

Micro fluidization

Multiple membrane extrusion method

Excipient Literature:

Cholesterol:

Functional category: Emulsifying agent, Emollient

Polysorbate 20

Polysorbate 40

Functional category: Nonionic surfactant, emulsifying agent, solubilizing agent, wetting agent.

Experimental Investigation:

Standard curve for Capecitabine (by UV method)

Optimization Process for Niosome Preparation

Formulation of Capecitabine Niosomes

Infrared Spectroscopic Studies

Evaluation Of Capecitabine Niosomes:

Removal of untrapped drug from niosomes

Encapsulation efficiency

In vitro release study for niosomal preparation

Zeta potential

Scanning electron microscopy

Sterility testing

Preparation of Soya bean Casein Digest medium (SCDM)

Preparation of Fluid Thioglycollate medium (FTM)

Preparation of Rinsing Fluid (Fluid A)

Stability study of Capecitabine Niosomes

Results And Discussion:

Development of Capecitabine niosomes:

In this study, Capecitabine loaded niosomes were prepared by thin film hydration technique using cholesterol and non-ionic surfactants such as span 20 and tween 20. Chloroform methanol mixture (2:1v/v) was used as solvent.

Formulations with different ratios of surfactant and cholesterol were prepared. Several physicochemical characteristics of niosomes such as morphology, vesicle size determination, drug release profile were investigated. And stability of optimized formulation at various temperatures was evaluated.

Optimization of process related variables:

The prepared niosomal vesicles were influenced by some factors like speed of rotation, hydration volume, hydration medium and vaccum. Before loading the drug, these factors should be optimized using empty vesicle.

Table 1: Optimization of process related variables

Surfactant : Cholesterol	Speed of Rotation (rpm)	Hydration Time (min)	Chloroform: methanol	Hydration Volume	Vesicle Size (μM)
100:100	75	30	2:1	5 ml	10.17 \pm 1.48
	100	60			9.39 \pm 1.09
	125	120			9.08 \pm 1.88
	150	120			8.42 \pm 1.73

Table 2: Optimization of process related variables

Volume of hydration medium (ml)	Hydration time (min)	Percentage entrapment (%)
3	60	58.13 \pm 0.93
4	60	64.81 \pm 0.70
4	60	68.38 \pm 0.49
5	120	86.42 \pm 0.88
5	180	79.36 \pm 0.92

IR studies:

Pressed Pellet Technique was used to handle the sample in FTIR spectrometer. In this technique a required amount of sample was added and mixed well with potassium bromide and the mixture was pressed with special discs under high pressure into a transparent pellet and then inserted into special holder of IR spectrometer. The pellets were scanned from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} in FTIR spectrophotometer and peaks obtained in both spectrums were identified.

Figure 1: IR Spectrum for Capecitabine

Figure 2: IR Spectrum for Capecitabine F10 Formulation

Table 3: IR Spectrum Frequencies for Capecitabine & F10 Formulation

Frequency		Group assigned
Pure drug	Physical mixture	
3402	3401	OH & NH - stretching
2852	2924	CH – stretching
1660	1654	C=O – stretching
1094	1106	CO – stretching

Evaluation Of Capecitabine Niosomes:

Removal of untrapped drug from Niosomes:

The untrapped drug from niosomes was removed by centrifugation technique. The results are presented in following table,

Percentage drug entrapment efficiency:

The entrapment efficiency of the niosomes is governed by the ability of formulation to retain drug molecule in aqueous core or in bilayer membrane of vesicles. After removal of unentrapped drug, the entrapment of all formulation was studied. Entrapment efficiency was varied with varying the surfactant and cholesterol ratio. Various factors like lipid concentration, drug to lipid ratio, and cholesterol content will change the entrapment efficiency.

Table 4: Percentage drug entrapment efficiency

Formulation code	Surfactant: Cholesterol (μM)	Surfactant used	Percentage of free Drug (%)	Percentage entrapment Efficiency (%)
F ₁	100:100	Span 20	46.91	53.09
F ₂	200:100	Span 20	41.44	58.56
F ₃	100:100	Span 40	53.68	46.32
F ₄	200:100	Span 40	48.91	51.09
F ₅	100:100	Tween 20	26.11	73.89
F ₆	200:100	Tween 20	23.35	76.65
F ₇	100:100	Tween 40	40.93	59.07
F ₈	200:100	Tween 40	35.09	64.10
F ₉	200:200	Tween 20	16.72	83.28
F ₁₀	300:200	Tween 20	6.05	93.95
F ₁₁	400:200	Tween 20	23.19	76.81

In vitro release study:

The release of Capecitabine from niosomes was determined using the membrane diffusion technique. Release study was carried for 24 hours and results are noted in following tables. The improve the entrapment efficiency surfactant formulation is F₁₀. Hence formulation F₁₀ was optimized one.

Table 5: *In vitro* drug release for F₁

Time (Hrs)	Amount of drug release (mg)	Cumulative % drug release (%)
1	5.0	5.0
2	9.03	9.04
3	15.07	15.08
4	19.60	19.64
5	25.16	25.19
6	31.20	31.22

7	36.81	36.84
8	39.54	39.57
9	42.97	42.99
10	47.95	48.01
11	50.38	50.45
12	54.09	54.12

Figure 3: In vitro drug release for F₁

Table 6: In vitro drug release for F₃

Time (Hrs)	Amount of drug release (mg)	Cumulative % drug release (%)
1	9.87	9.87
2	15.87	15.89
3	19.41	19.43
4	25.77	25.79
5	30.86	30.87
6	38.20	38.23
7	42.68	42.76
8	46.97	47

Figure 4: *In vitro* drug release for F₃

Table 7: *In vitro* drug release for F₅

Time (Hrs)	Amount of drug release (mg)	Cumulative % drug release (%)
1	4.0	4.0
2	8.02	8.04
3	11.06	11.08
4	19.10	19.11
5	22.17	22.19
6	34.20	34.22
7	36.33	36.34
8	39.34	39.36
9	41.37	41.39
10	44.40	44.41
11	48.43	48.45
12	53.45	53.47
13	56.55	56.57
14	61.09	61.31

Figure 5: In vitro drug release for F₅

Table 8: In vitro drug release for F₈

Time (Hrs)	Amount of drug release (mg)	Cumulative drug release (%)
1	9.0	9.0
2	14.08	14.09
3	15.13	15.14
4	19.14	19.15
5	24.17	24.19
6	29.22	29.24
7	32.27	32.29
8	35.31	35.32
9	36.34	36.35
10	41.35	41.36
11	48.40	48.41
12	51.47	51.48
13	53.50	53.51
14	58.52	58.53
15	61.57	61.58

16	68.60	68.61
17	74.64	74.68
18	79.69	79.74

Figure 6: In vitro drug release for F₈

Table 9: In vitro drug release for F₁₀

Time (Hrs)	Amount of drug release(mg)	Cumulative % drug release (%)
1	6	6
2	10.11	10.12
3	14.18	14.19
4	18.20	18.21
5	23.22	23.23
6	26.23	26.24
7	30.27	30.29
8	34.30	34.31
9	38.37	38.39
10	42.40	42.41
11	46.42	46.44
12	50.47	50.48
13	52.4	52.5
14	55.50	55.52
15	58.53	58.54
16	62.56	62.57
17	67.57	67.58
18	71.62	71.64
19	75.66	75.68
20	79.67	79.69
21	82.74	82.75

22	85.77	85.79
23	89.80	89.84
24	92.79	92.86

Figure 7: In vitro drug release for F₁₀

Table 10: In vitro drug release for F₁₁

Time (Hrs)	Amount of drug release (mg)	Cumulative % drug release (%)
1	5.0	5.0
2	10.04	10.05
3	16.09	16.10
4	18.15	18.16
5	23.16	23.18
6	29.22	29.23
7	31.27	31.29
8	32.30	32.31
9	35.31	35.32
10	39.34	39.35
11	42.37	42.39
12	44.40	44.42
13	49.43	49.44
14	50.47	50.49
15	52.48	52.50

16	57.50	57.52
17	60.56	60.57
18	62.59	62.60
19	67.61	67.62
20	70.57	70.59

Figure 8: In vitro drug release for F₁₁

In vitro drug release was carried out for 24 hours using phosphate buffer as diffusion medium. It was found to be biphasic, and the release was controlled by lipid bilayer and dialysis membrane. Incorporation of cholesterol affected the release rate of encapsulated drug. *In vitro* drug release characteristics for formulations containing two different surfactants were compared. Capecitabine niosomes were tried with two different surfactant and cholesterol concentrations. Higher release was found in F₁₀ formulation contained 300:200 μmol ratio of surfactant and cholesterol. So formulation F₁₀ (300:200μmol) was considered as optimized formulation.

Figure 9: Comparative *invitro* release study of Capecitabine niosomal formulations
Scanning electron microscopy:

The surface characteristics of Capecitabine niosomal formulation were studied by scanning electron microscopy. SEM image of prepared niosome formulation shows that the coating of surfactant cholesterol mixture on drug particles. The appearance of niosome vesicles in scanning electron micrograph is smooth, which indicates a thin and uniform coating over the drug. Based on the scale of micrograph, no significant change in size of particles is seen. The observation clearly shows that, there is no aggregation between the particles, due to surfactant coating.

The surface characteristics of optimized formulation (F10) particle size were studied by scanning electron microscopy. SEM image of prepared nanoparticle formulation shows the coating of polymer mixture on drug particles. The size distribution of nanoparticles indicates a thin and uniform coating over the drug.

Zeta potential:

The addition of membrane additives affects zeta potential value depending on the type of membrane additives. Zeta potential of optimized Capecitabine niosome formulation was measured and found to 54 mv. The negative zeta potential observed with niosomes reflects the presence of negatively charged DCP on the surface of vesicles. The obtained result of the zeta potential of the prepared formulation indicates particles in the formulation remains suspended and so were found to be stable. The particles being suspended. The formulation was found to be very effective for parenteral administration.

Sterility test:

The Capecitabine niosomes was subjected to sterility test as per specifications of Indian Pharmacopoeia. Both Soya bean casein Digest medium (SCDM) and Fluid Thioglycolate medium (FTM) were used. The positive control was prepared by standardized Bacillus Subtilis suspension. The method followed is Method A - membrane filtration method. The samples dipped in SCDM and FTM were observed for 14 days and photographed. The absence of turbidity of the medium used for the test indicated the sterility of the formulation and passed the sterility test.

Stability studies:

The optimized Capecitabine niosomal formulation (F₁₀) was subjected to stability study for three months at 4°C, room temperature and 45°C/75%RH. At the interval of one month the niosomes evaluated for *in vitro* release and entrapment efficiency. The stability study shows that niosomal formulations are more stable at 4°C (refrigerator) when compared to room temperature and at 45°C/75%RH.

Table 11: In vitro data for optimized formulation F10 at Room temperature

Time (Hrs)	Cumulative % drug release		
	1 st month (%)	2 nd month (%)	3 rd month (%)
1	7.0	5.0	5.0
2	9.07	7.05	7.05
3	12.09	13.07	14.07
4	16.12	17.13	20.14
5	19.08	24.17	22.20
6	23.19	29.24	26.22
7	24.23	31.29	27.26
8	29.24	34.31	32.27
9	33.29	39.34	34.32
10	34.33	45.39	37.34
11	39.34	47.45	39.37

12	41.39	49.47	42.38
13	45.41	51.49	44.42
14	47.45	53.51	48.42
15	49.47	56.53	50.48
16	50.49	61.56	51.50
17	62.50	63.61	58.51
18	63.62	68.63	60.58
19	69.63	69.68	66.60
20	70.69	71.69	67.66
21	76.70	72.71	69.67
22	79.76	77.72	74.69
23	83.79	80.77	77.74
24	85.83	82.80	78.77

Figure 10: Stability Study Release Data for Formulation F10 After Three Months at Room Temperature

Conclusion:

From the results of the present experiment, it may be concluded that formulation F10 showing high percentage of entrapment and desired sustained release of Capecitabine. Hence F10 formulation was the optimized one. The prepared microspheres were able to pass all the evaluation parameters which are necessary for the ideal properties of Niosomes. The prolonged release of the drug from the niosomes suggests that the frequency of administration may be reduced. Further, as the particles are in nanometric size distribution range, the bioavailability may be increased and effective targeting may be achieved. The optimized formulation F10 was found to follow Zero order release pattern which was revealed by the linearity shown from the plot of time versus concentration. Future investigations pharmacological and toxicological investigations in animals and human volunteers may help to exploit the niosomes as prosperous drug carriers for targeting

drugs more efficiently. Hence, conclude that niosomes provide controlled release of drug and these systems are used as drug carriers for the delivery of cytotoxic drugs with fewer side effects.

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